

Studies on Th(IV) and Zr(IV) Complexes of Oxygen Donor Ligands. Part XII. Oxozirconium(IV) Complexes of 2-methyl pyridine N-oxide*

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A new series of five and seven coordinate complexes of oxozirconium(IV) of the type $ZrO(picO)_2X_2$ ($X=Cl, Br, NO_2$ or NCS) and $ZrO(picO)_4X_2$ ($X=ClO_4$ or I), (where $picO=2$ methyl pyridine N-oxide) have been synthesised and characterised by conventional technique including far i.r. In all the complexes $picO$ is bonded through the lone oxygen atom. Thermal behaviour of the complexes has also been investigated.

RECENTLY a large number of coordination compounds of pyridine N-oxide (PYO) and its ring substituted derivatives with a wide variety of metal salts have been synthesised and characterised¹⁻³. Pyridine N-oxide and its 3- or 4-substituted derivatives do not introduce steric effects during coordination to metal ions¹. In the cases of 2- or 2,6-substituted pyridine N-oxides, steric factors become important in stabilization of complexes⁴⁻⁶. However, in the case of oxozirconium(IV) complexes of 2,6-dimethylpyridine N-oxide, the steric repulsion between the two ligand groups is less severe because of the large ionic radius of the metal ion^{6,7}. Comparatively very little is known about the compounds of oxozirconium(IV) with aromatic amine N-oxide⁷⁻¹². The present paper deals with the synthesis and characterisation of complexes of 2-methyl pyridine N-oxide ($picO$) with oxozirconium(IV) salts.

Experimental

Materials employed $ZrO(NO_3)_2 \cdot 5H_2O$ and $ZrOCl_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ were obtained from B.D.H. Anhydrous $ZrOCl_2$ prepared as reported earlier¹³. Crystalline zirconyl perchlorate was prepared by established method¹⁴. Other zirconyl halides were prepared as follows: Methanolic solutions of anhydrous $ZrOCl_2$ and KX ($X=Br, I, SCN$) were mixed in 1:2 equimolar ratio and stirred the reaction mixture on a magnetic stirrer for 0.5h. The precipitated KCl was filtered off and filtrate containing $ZrOX_2$ was used for the preparation of the complexes.

2-Methyl pyridine N-oxide was obtained from Aldrich Chemical Company, Inc., U.S.A.

Preparation of the Complexes :

A solution of oxozirconium salt in methanol was treated with an excess of the $picO$, in the same solvent. The mixture was refluxed on waterbath for *ca.* 3h and the excess solvent was removed by distillation. The residual mass on treatment with diethyl-ether yielded a crystalline solid which was filtered off, washed several times with solvent ether and dried under vacuum over anhydrous $CaCl_2$.

Analysis :

The metal content of the complexes was determined as earlier⁸. The perchlorate was determined by the method of Kurz¹⁵. The halide in the complexes was determined by Volhard's method, while the thiocyanate was determined by titration of a slightly acidic solution of the complex against standard silver-nitrate.

The electrical conductance measurements of the complexes were carried out with a Toshniwal conductivity bridge at room-temperature. The molecular weight of the complexes was determined cryoscopically in freezing nitrobenzene. The i.r. spectra of the complexes were recorded in the 4000-200 cm^{-1} range using Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer model 521 and Beckmann I.R.-12. The d.t. a. were

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL CONDUCTIVITY AND MOLECULAR WEIGHT DATA OF OXOZIRCONIUM (IV) COMPLEXES OF 2-METHYL-PYRIDINE-N-OXIDE

Complex	Colour	Zr% Found (Calcd)	O% Found (Calcd)	N% Found (Calcd)	H% Found (Calcd)	Anion% Found (Calcd)	Λ_m $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$ in PhNO_2 in DMSO	Electrolytic nature	Mol. wt. Found (Calcd)	
ZrOCl ₂ ·2picO	Light yellow	22.39 (22.97)	36.13 (36.36)	7.28 (7.07)	3.47 (3.53)	17.80 (17.92)	2.8	10.9	Non-electrolytic	372 (396)
ZrOBr ₂ ·2picO	Grey	18.54 (18.76)	29.24 (29.69)	5.93 (5.77)	2.67 (2.88)	32.42 (32.98)	1.7	9.3	Non-electrolytic	467 (485)
ZrOI ₂ ·4picO	Brown	11.20 (11.41)	35.90 (36.13)	7.42 (7.02)	3.32 (3.51)	31.10 (31.66)	49.7	78.7	1 : 2	257 (797)
ZrO(CO ₃) ₂ ·picO	Reddish yellow	11.98 (12.26)	39.01 (38.81)	7.32 (7.54)	3.42 (3.77)	26.10 (26.82)	51.3	83.9	1 : 2	239 (742)
ZrO(NO ₃) ₂ ·picO	Creamish	19.98 (20.26)	32.32 (32.07)	12.26 (12.47)	3.40 (3.11)	— (27.61)	2.3	9.8	Non-electrolytic	417 (449)
ZrO(NCS) ₂ ·2picO	Muddy	38.67 (20.63)	12.43 (38.09)	12.43 (12.69)	3.37 (3.17)	25.90 (26.30)	1.6	8.6	Non-electrolytic	423 (441)

carried out in air atmosphere using DTA-02. Universal (DDR) using alumina as reference substance and the heating rate was 10°min^{-1} , while t.g.a. were done on Cahn R.G.-Electrobalance with platinum boat in static air and the heating rate was 6°min^{-1} .

Results and Discussion

The interaction of oxozirconium(IV) salts with 2-picO results in the formation of $\text{ZrO}(\text{picO})_2\text{X}_2$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{NO}_3, \text{NCS}$) and $\text{ZrO}(\text{picO})_4\text{X}_2$ ($\text{X} = \text{ClO}_4, \text{I}$). Analysis of the complexes are given in Table 1. The complexes have high melting points and sufficiently soluble in polar solvents and insoluble in non-polar solvents. The molar conductance-values in nitrobenzene and sulphoxide indicate that the chloro, bromo, nitrate and thiocyanato. Complexes are non-electrolytes while the iodo and perchlorato complexes behave like 1 : 2 electrolyte. The molecular weight determination of the complexes also support the same electrolytic nature of the complexes. The types of the complexes isolated during the present study have 1 : 2 or 1 : 4 stoichiometry with different oxozirconium(IV) salts. Previous workers^{7,8} have shown that with PyO and LNO formed complexes of 1 : 2, 1 : 4 and 1 : 6 stoichiometry with different oxozirconium salts. A comparison of the nature of the three ligands with oxozirconium(IV) salts. Thus clearly indicates the steric hindrance introduced in the complex formation by the presence of the 2-methyl substituent in picO.

Infrared Studies :

In coordination of the amine-oxide to a metal ion through the NO oxygen generally influenced. The three main vibration frequencies, (NO stretching vibration, NO bending vibration and C—H ring out-of-plane deformation) of amine oxides¹⁶.

In the spectra of the free picO the NO stretching vibration appears as a strong band at 1245cm^{-1} ^{17,18} in nujol-mull while at 1265cm^{-1} in KBr¹⁹, which

suffers a significant negative shift on complexation with oxozirconium(IV) salts (Table 2). The decrease in the frequency of the NO stretching vibration is attributed to coordination from the oxygen atom of the base causing a decrease in π character of the N—O bond^{16,20}.

 TABLE 2—PERTINENT IR SPECTRAL DATA (cm^{-1}) OF ZrO(IV) COMPLEXES OF 2-picO

Complex	$\gamma(\text{NO})$	$\delta(\text{NO})$	γCH out-of-plane deformation	$\gamma(\text{MO})$
ZrOCl ₂ ·2picO	1220s	810m	800s, 780s	382m
ZrOBr ₂ ·2picO	1218m	820m	800s, 755s	380m
ZrOI ₂ ·4picO	1215s	820m	790s, 755s	385m
ZrO(ClO ₄) ₂ ·4picO	1220s	815m	790m, 780m	390m
ZrO(NO ₃) ₂ ·2picO	1210m	810m	795s, 760m	400m
ZrO(NCS) ₂ ·2picO	1220s	810m	790s, 780m	390m

An absorption of strong intensity at 845cm^{-1} ¹⁹ has been assigned to NO bending mode and from the tabulated data, it is apparent that only a slight shift of this vibration is observed on complexation¹⁹. Absorption associated with C—H out-of-plane deformation modes assigned at 773 and 730cm^{-1} are supposed to undergo slight positive shift due to tightening of the aromatic ring on complexation¹⁹. A positive shift of *ca.* 10cm^{-1} has been observed in this mode of vibration which is in conformity with the observations of earlier workers¹⁷⁻¹⁹. The characteristic, Zr=O stretching frequency has been observed as a weak band in all the complexes at *ca.* 960cm^{-1} ^{10,21}.

In the region $400-350 \text{cm}^{-1}$, there is a characteristic medium or weak band in the complexes. Where the ligand itself has no absorption. These new bands in this region are tentatively assigned^{9,10,21} as $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ frequencies.

The presence of numerous bands in the spectra of picO complexes of ZrO(IV) complicates the identification of the nature of coordination of the

perchlorate, nitrate and thiocynate groups. However, a close comparison of the spectra makes some inference possible.

In $ZrO(picO)_6(ClO_4)_2$, the very strong ν_3 band and a strong ν_4 band are assigned to the bands observed at *ca.* 1085 and *ca.* 625 cm^{-1} , respectively, for the perchlorate ion, indicating that Td symmetry has not been disturbed and the perchlorate ions are not bonded to the zirconium ion^{8,10,21}.

The absence on the ν_3 band of ionic nitrate (D_{3h}) around *ca.* 1360 cm^{-1} and the occurrence of two strong bands at *ca.* 1520 and 1280 cm^{-1} in spectra of nitrate complex suggest the coordination of nitrate in these complexes^{22,23}. Conclusive decision between mono and bidentate nature of nitrate groups is rather difficult. However, by applying Lever separation method²⁴, the two combination ($\nu_1 + \nu_4$) bands appear at 1760 and 1700 cm^{-1} . The separation is 60 cm^{-1} which suggest the bidentate nature of the nitrate groups in this complex. The bidentate nature of nitrate groups further supported by the presence of bands at *ca.* 1020 cm^{-1} (ν_2), *ca.* 800 cm^{-1} (ν_6) and *ca.* 730 cm^{-1} (ν_8/ν_9)²⁵.

In the thiocynato complex, $ZrO(picO)_2(NCS)_2$, the C=N stretching vibration is observed at *ca.* 2040 cm^{-1} . This may be taken as an evidence for the bending of the thiocynate through nitrogen in the ZrO(IV) complex²⁶. The $\nu(CS)$ and $\delta(NCS)$ frequencies observed at 780 cm^{-1} and 480 cm^{-1} respectively further support the N-bonding to zirconium ion.

Thermal Behaviour :

The thermal investigations of zirconium(IV) complexes of amine N-oxides have been investigated to only a limited extent⁷⁻⁹. The d.t.a. of the complexes studied in reveal no peak around 100° indicating the non-hygroscopic nature of the complexes. The chloro, bromo and nitrate complexes decompose endothermically while thiocynato and perchlorato complexes decompose exothermically, the later decomposing violently due to the oxygen content of the perchlorate. On decomposition, all the complexes produce carbon and metal. The small exo-peak around 400° is due to oxidation of carbon, while a final sharp exo-peak around 550° is due to complete metal oxidation.

The thermogravimetric analysis of the complexes also show the similar thermal behaviour. No change occurs upto 150°. The weight loss values observed in the thermal decomposition of oxozirconium(IV) complexes of picO correspond very closely with the

following schemes :

If the minimum t.g.a. decomposition temperature is taken as a rough criterion of the thermal stability then the order for oxozirconium(IV) complexes with picO is $ClO_4 < NO_3 < Cl < Br < NCS$.

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